

METAPHOR IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS AND THE PHILOSOPHY OF LANGUAGE: FROM RHETORICAL DEVICE TO COGNITIVE MECHANISM

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Abstract

The transformation of fundamental philosophical paradigms in the twentieth century gave rise to a new approach to the understanding of metaphor. Whereas in classical philosophy language was regarded primarily as a secondary means of expressing thought, twentieth-century philosophy increasingly conceptualised language as a productive mechanism of consciousness through which human beings construct and apprehend the reality of their own existence. Within this framework, metaphor comes to be seen as a key analytical tool for investigating the cognitive processes underlying thinking, perception, and world knowledge. As a universal cognitive mechanism, metaphor contributes to the formation of the world picture and plays a significant role in the biological and cultural evolution of humankind.

Keywords: metaphor theory, cognition, thinking, cognitive linguistics, philosophy of language.

In the twentieth century, philosophy underwent profound transformations: classical rationalism gave way to irrationalist approaches, including existentialism and the philosophy of life. The reconfiguration of fundamental philosophical assumptions significantly contributed to the emergence of a new perspective on metaphor, the scholarly interest in which began to expand “like ripples on water from a stone thrown in” [16, p. 3]. This shift was driven by a change in the scientific paradigm of the humanities, which placed the human being and human activity - particularly processes of cognition and understanding of the surrounding world - at its centre. Language, which in classical philosophy had been regarded merely as a vehicle or shell of thought, became in the twentieth century a central object of philosophical inquiry, inseparable from human consciousness. A consistent approach to language that diverged from the dominant logical formalism was proposed by Ludwig Wittgenstein in his philosophical writings, where he argued that language should be understood not simply as a means of expressing thought, but as a creative instrument of consciousness enabling humans to model and construct the reality of their existence. The emergence of the anthropocentric paradigm led to a reorientation of linguistic inquiry towards the human being and their place in the world and in culture. The foundational principle of contemporary linguistic research - “the human being in language” - is closely connected with existential philosophy. According to Heidegger, it is precisely in language that the possibility of fulfilling one’s highest human vocation is grounded, since language is the human capacity to “say Being”. Such an understanding of the nature of language has been adopted today by both philosophers and linguists.

The new paradigm presupposes new research orientations and objectives, as well as new key concepts and methodologies. Modern linguistics actively develops approaches in which language is viewed as a means of cognition and as a cultural code of a people. Language does not mirror the world like a

reflection; rather, it interprets the world and constructs the reality in which humans live. It is no longer examined “in itself and for itself”; instead, within the new paradigm, language is analysed in terms of its participation in human cognitive activity. This reorientation accounts for the growing scholarly interest in metaphor. At the same time, “the centre of gravity in metaphor studies has shifted towards the analysis of actual language use and towards domains concerned with thinking, cognition, and consciousness, with conceptual systems, and ultimately with the modelling of artificial intelligence. Metaphor has come to be regarded as a key to understanding the foundations of thought and the processes involved in constructing not only culturally specific worldviews, but also their universal representations” [1, pp. 5–6].

Twentieth-century research on metaphor within cognitive linguistics, psychology, philosophy, psycholinguistics, and linguocultural studies demonstrates that metaphor is not merely a linguistic phenomenon but a universal cognitive mechanism - one of the fundamental ways in which the world is perceived. The study of metaphorisation processes and the underlying cognitive structures, including their universal and culture-specific features, makes it possible to gain insight into the nature of human cognitive activity associated with understanding and producing linguistic expressions. As one author notes, “the recognition of the self as the measure of all things grants human beings the right to create an anthropocentric order of reality within consciousness - an order that can be investigated not at the everyday level but at the scientific one. This order, existing in the human mind, determines spiritual essence, motives of action, and value hierarchies. All of this can be understood through the analysis of human speech, of those turns of phrase and expressions that are used most frequently and evoke the highest degree of empathy” [10, pp. 6–7].

Before metaphor came to be recognised as a crucial cognitive instrument, however, it underwent a long and contested process of legitimisation.

Throughout much of the twentieth century, debates about metaphor persisted. Many linguists and philosophers regarded metaphor as a marker of imprecise or careless thinking. In their view, metaphors were employed either by mystics to “express rapture at the moment of uniting the incompatible”, or by poets to articulate intuitive sensations and impressions. Philosophical rationalists were particularly hostile towards metaphor. T. Hobbes famously argued that the light of the human mind consists in clear words purified of ambiguity, whereas “metaphors and ambiguous expressions are like ignes fatui (will-o’-the-wisps), and reasoning with them is nothing but wandering among innumerable absurdities, leading ultimately to contention, disturbance, or contempt” [4]. Despite the fact that he himself relied on a metaphor in this very statement. Logical positivists, empiricists, and representatives of analytic philosophy likewise rejected metaphor, considering it inadmissible in scientific discourse and comparing the use of metaphor to the commission of a crime. Many scholars, following the classical tradition, insisted on the incompatibility of scientific theories with metaphor. As M. Bunge, a proponent of so-called “scientific materialism”, claimed, “to suppose that scientific explanation is metaphorical is to confuse scientific theory with biblical parables” (M. Bunge, *Philosophy of Physics*). Philosophical irrationalism, by contrast, adopted an entirely different stance, effectively granting metaphor primacy in the domain of cognition. F. Nietzsche drew attention to the role of metaphor in knowledge and in the construction of worldviews, emphasising its epistemological function. He argued that cognition is fundamentally metaphorical: “This drive to form metaphors is the fundamental human drive, which cannot be ignored for even a moment, for in doing so we would ignore humanity itself...” [12]. This view reflects the position of Romantic philosophers, for whom metaphor was not merely a means of expressing thought, but a condition of thinking itself.

In the 1960s and 1970s, postmodernism revised traditional scientific values, prompting a reassessment of the role of metaphor in science. The neo-positivist demand to eliminate ambiguity from scientific language ultimately proved untenable. By this time, it had become clear that the pursuit of absolute univocity leads to the impoverishment of scientific language and the reduction of its cognitive potential, thereby hindering further scientific development. As early as Locke, attention had been drawn to the fact that understanding complex - and especially novel - theories is often impeded by the lack of adequate means for expressing new concepts. At initial stages, this deficiency may be partially remedied through the metaphorical use of existing terms. Consequently, the metaphorical nature of scientific terminology has persisted and will continue to persist, owing to the open-ended character of cognition. Studies of scientific language have confirmed the presence of a substantial number of terms and statements that are metaphorical in origin and content. Subsequent research into the role of metaphor in the development of scientific language has revealed the reasons for its prevalence in

terminology: metaphor is capable of expressing hypotheses while simultaneously directing the interpretation of the object under investigation. “Model metaphors” function as heuristic devices for exploring objects of complex nature, though they do not constitute theories themselves. Such models are typically constructed in two stages: initially, researchers rely on intuition, experience, analogy, and metaphor; subsequently, these primary intuitions are modelled and subjected to analytical scrutiny. Metaphorical explanation thus pertains to the theory-building phase rather than to final definition. It is evident that metaphor plays a crucial role in the humanities, forming the foundation of fundamental theoretical constructs. As M. L. Mot’ko observes, “metaphor in the humanities operates at all levels of cognition - from the deep level, where one may speak of fundamental or basic metaphors, to the surface level, where illustrative metaphors are used to clarify the meaning of specific fragments and terms” [11]. Metaphor is not only a means of expression but also an essential instrument of thought: “Metaphor serves as the tool by which we reach the most distant regions of our conceptual field. Objects that are close and readily comprehensible open access to remote and elusive concepts. Metaphor lengthens the ‘arm’ of the intellect; its role in logic may be likened to that of a fishing rod or a rifle” [13, pp. 71–72].

The American philosopher Max Black, who investigated the cognitive functions of metaphor, explicitly linked it to scientific inquiry: “Metaphors are dangerous—perhaps most dangerous in philosophy. But to ban their use is deliberately to limit the powers of our minds in the pursuit of discovery” [2, p. 159]. He viewed metaphor as a phenomenon emerging in the movement of thought and contributing to the development of a language’s conceptual apparatus. Daniel N. Robinson similarly notes that “science is a human enterprise, and however narrow or specialised it may become, however dull or esoteric its problems and methods, it rarely escapes the habits of the human mind. One of the most persistent habits is the imposition of metaphors and analogies in attempts to understand elusive phenomena. And among all elusive phenomena, none is more subtle and vivid than the mind itself” [15, pp. 331–332].

The modelling function of metaphor - its capacity to stimulate thought and guide researchers towards new analogies - has been emphasised by many scholars (S. S. Gusev, E. A. Lapinya, R. Boyd, among others). Metaphor brings us closer to understanding the true nature of the phenomena under investigation. Lapinya points out that once a metaphor has fulfilled its cognitive role in the formation of a scientific hypothesis and concept, it gradually loses its metaphorical status and becomes established as an independent nominative unit. T. Kuhn, in turn, argues that the cognitive function of metaphors lies in their ability to generate new connections during periods of scientific paradigm change, which are typically accompanied by shifts in so-called basic or key metaphors.

Key metaphors are defined as those that “map the image of one fragment of reality onto another, enabling

its conceptualisation by analogy with an already established system of concepts” [1, p. 14]. While basic metaphors had previously been of primary interest to cultural theorists and ethnographers studying culturally specific worldviews, in the twentieth century they became objects of investigation in the psychology of thinking and the methodology of science. It has become evident that scientists and philosophers, implicitly or explicitly, employ basic metaphors in their theoretical constructions. For example, the dominant cultural idea of the seventeenth century was mechanistic in spirit, and the universe was conceived as a machine. The metaphor of the clock reflected this mechanistic worldview: over time, clocks came to be perceived as models of the universe as a whole. Johannes Kepler, Robert Boyle, and René Descartes all argued that the universe was nothing other than a “magnificent clockwork mechanism”, with God as the supreme clockmaker. Humans, too, came to be perceived as a kind of mechanism - a view that gained prominence in philosophy and literature (e.g. Mary Wollstonecraft Shelley’s *Frankenstein*, L. Frank Baum’s *The Wizard of Oz*).

In the twentieth century, the clock ceased to function as the dominant model of the universe, giving way to a more complex mechanism: the computer. Increasingly, computational terminology has been used to conceptualise cognition, while computers themselves have been described in terms of human activity. The basic metaphor “human being as computer” gave rise to the more specific metaphor “mind as machine”, which is directly reflected in language. The presence of basic metaphors can be traced across virtually all domains of knowledge. Even the logical positivists of the early twentieth century, who claimed to reject all a priori principles, implicitly assumed that language functions as a mirror of the world.

In the second half of the twentieth century, the interaction among various humanities disciplines - psychology, philosophy, hermeneutics, cultural studies, semiotics, linguistics, psycholinguistics, and others - contributed to the formation of what is commonly referred to as cognitive science. This field is grounded in the assumption that human cognitive structures (perception, language, thinking, memory) are interconnected in the shared task of acquiring, processing, and transforming knowledge, which ultimately defines the nature of the human mind. Within cognitive linguistics, the central category is knowledge and the ways in which it is represented. Language serves as the primary means of encoding, storing, processing, and transmitting information. It enables individuals to organise and systematise vast amounts of knowledge in memory and to construct a linguistic worldview characteristic of a particular ethnocultural community. Language acts as a mediator in the processes of information transmission and reception, while simultaneously processing information and thus generating linguistic frames. As a result, “actual ontological fragments of the world acquire topological features in the naïve worldview reflected in language. For example, metaphorisation -

the principal mental operation and a means of understanding and explaining the world - is associated with representing new knowledge through existing knowledge (e.g. *river arm*). Humans do not merely express thoughts through metaphors; they think in metaphors, which presupposes self-interpretability: semantic fields, networks of meanings, hybrid semantics, semantic space, the integration of multiple theories, the centre of the semantic field, and so forth” [9, pp. 10–11].

Cognitive linguistics identifies image schemas through which humans conceptualise the surrounding world. According to M. Johnson’s theory of image schemas, these are recurrent dynamic patterns of perceptual interaction that subsequently structure more abstract concepts. In cognitive processes, complex mental spaces are mapped onto familiar ones via metaphor (for example, economic or political actions are conceptualised as games or sporting competitions, and industrial conflicts as war). From a cognitive perspective, metaphor involves understanding and representing certain meanings in terms of others. Because metaphor constitutes a universal cognitive mechanism, it assumes particular importance in cognitive linguistics, especially in relation to issues such as worldview construction, concepts, and conceptual systems.

The idea that metaphor constitutes a form of thought is reflected in various interaction theories (A. Richards, M. Black, W. Aldridge, M. Hester, P. Hesse), which explore the mechanisms of metaphor. These theories converge on the conclusion that metaphorical thought is fundamentally linked to imagination. Metaphor thus came to be viewed as the result of cognitive – imaginative activity. Max Black’s interactive theory of metaphor conceptualises metaphor as an associative interaction between two conceptual domains, structured around a focus and a frame, whereby one system functions as a filter for another. This approach has been interpreted as a variation of Wittgenstein’s notion of “aspect seeing”. Similar views are shared by W. Aldridge and M. Hester, who emphasise the role of imaginative perspective in metaphorical understanding.

The hermeneutic approach to metaphor is associated with the work of Paul Ricoeur, whose model assigns a central role to imagination and sensation. As Ricoeur argues, imagination “is not reducible either to the simple schematisation of predicative assimilation through synthetic apprehension of similarities, or to the mere illustration of meanings by images; rather, it participates in the projection of new ways of redescribing the world”. Imagination thus provides models for perceiving reality in novel ways.

In 1976, the American scholar Julian Jaynes published *The Origin of Consciousness in the Breakdown of the Bicameral Mind*, a work that devoted a separate chapter to metaphor. Jaynes linked the evolution of consciousness to the capacity for metaphorisation, viewing metaphor as a means of expanding human understanding of the world and of extending consciousness itself [3, p. 16].

In the 1980s, George Lakoff and Mark Johnson published the influential book *Metaphors We Live By* (1980), which introduced a fundamentally new approach to metaphor and had a lasting impact on subsequent research. They proposed the theory of conceptual metaphors that structure everyday thinking and language. According to their hypothesis, imagery in speech does not arise from the interaction of individual word meanings, as assumed in traditional theories, but is rooted in cognition itself. The authors argue that the concepts governing our thinking extend beyond the realm of intellect to shape everyday activity and behaviour. Conceptual systems structure perceived reality, modes of action, and social interaction; consequently, they play a central role in defining everyday reality. If, as Lakoff and Johnson contend, our conceptual system is largely metaphorical in nature, then thinking, experience, and behaviour are to a significant extent shaped by metaphor [7, p. 387]. Drawing on linguistic evidence, they concluded that the ordinary conceptual system within which we think and act is inherently metaphorical. For example, the conceptual metaphor *argument is war* is reflected in everyday expressions such as *defend one's position*, *attack an argument*, *win or lose an argument*, and *force one's opponent to retreat*. Although arguments and wars are fundamentally different phenomena, we conceptualise arguments as warlike confrontations, often without conscious awareness. In this sense, *argument is war* exemplifies the metaphors by which we “live” within a given culture. Linguistic metaphors are possible because metaphorical structures exist within the conceptual system itself. Since metaphor involves transforming context and, indirectly, reshaping shared associations, it functions as a powerful means of cognition and social transformation.

A detailed analysis of metaphor as a mode of thinking within cognitive linguistics is presented in Earl MacCormac's *A Cognitive Theory of Metaphor*. Drawing on psychological and linguistic data, MacCormac provides philosophical arguments for treating metaphor as a cognitive process. Viewed from within, metaphors function as cognitive mechanisms through which we deepen our understanding of the world and generate new hypotheses; viewed from without, they mediate between human cognition and culture. New metaphors transform everyday language and alter modes of perception and understanding. As metaphors become conventionalised, they expand lexical inventories; over time, some metaphors fade or “die”. By influencing language, metaphor contributes to cultural evolution and may even affect biological evolution. This dual involvement allows metaphor to be regarded as an integral component of what has been termed “evolutionary epistemology” [8, p. 360].

In twentieth-century metaphor studies, the cognitive approach has become dominant. The claim that conceptual metaphors permeate all domains of human experience and possess significant cognitive potential is supported by contemporary research. Interdisciplinary studies have proliferated, examining the role of metaphor in scientific knowledge acquisition, worldview formation, and human

biological and cultural evolution. At this stage, several complementary approaches to metaphor research can be distinguished, including classical conceptual metaphor theory (Lakoff, Johnson), the coherence model of metaphor (Spellman), conceptual projection and blending theory (Turner, Fauconnier), the theory of primary and complex metaphors (Grady), the connective theory of metaphorical interpretation (Ritchie), analyses of linguistic metaphorical expressions as derivatives of conceptual metaphors (Allbritton), studies of metaphorical truth and falsity (Ortony, Gerrig), investigations of metaphor as a means of linking informational units in memory (McKoon, Ratcliff, Seifert), the descriptor theory of metaphor (Baranov, Karaulov), and others.

In conclusion, as a result of the transformation of fundamental philosophical assumptions in the twentieth century, views on language underwent a radical shift. Language came to be understood not as a mere vehicle of thought, but as a creative instrument of cognition and world-modelling. Accordingly, metaphor - once regarded as a rhetorical ornament - was recognised as a crucial means of thinking, knowing, and perceiving reality, and as a driving force in the development of human consciousness. Cognitive metaphor theory gained widespread recognition during the twentieth century and continues to develop actively. It is precisely its interdisciplinary character that has made it possible to approach a deeper understanding of the phenomenon of metaphor.

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